

Passive Mechanical Heat/Mass Exchange Enhancement by Semi-Confined Laminar Parallel Wall Jets

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Abstract

Many different approaches have been investigated in the literature to achieve efficient heat and mass exchangers in applications in several fields such as mechanical, aeronautical or biomedical engineering. Some of these engineering devices need to efficiently mix two fluids at different temperature or concentrations, achieving a decent mixing at a low power cost, and using passive mechanical elements if possible. This paper introduces and analyses numerically the novel application of two parallel wall jets to enhance mixing by vortex shedding induced mechanically. The numerical approach is the non-uniform finite difference approximation, used for the first time in the study of mixing mechanics. The parallel wall jets are constrained within a channel, which can be a simple and passive easily manufactured machine with high potential as scalable laminar mixing device. Different wall jet geometries and Reynolds numbers have been tested with a verified&validated CFD code based on non-uniform finite difference approximation. This analysis allowed to predict configurations that lead to unsteady oscillatory motion. In general, it has been observed that for a range of laminar wall jets, a small channel ratio seems a very efficient option for heat/mass transfer, thanks to the intense oscillation generated in the flow downstream, which enhances mixing with low power requirement.

Keywords: CFD, heat transfer, mass transfer, mixing machines, mechanical engineering

Nomenclature

Roman Symbols

$\langle - \rangle$	Time-averaged value.
\vec{v}	Velocity vector.
C	Solute concentration/Temperature.
C_0	Characteristic solute concentration/temperature.
D	Thermal diffusivity/molecular diffusivity.
f	Oscillation frequency.
g	Arbitrary magnitude.
H	Channel width.
h	Wall jet width.
h'	Distance from the channel wall to the opposite wall jet.
L	Channel total length.
mec	Mixing energy cost.
N_x	Total number of nodes in the x direction.
N_y	Total number of nodes in the y direction.
ny_1	Number of nodes along the wall jet width in the y direction.
ny_2	Number of nodes along the zone between wall jets in the y direction.
p	Pressure.
Pe	Peclet-like number.
q	2D channel flow rate.
q_j	2D wall jet flow rate.
Re	Reynolds number.
St	Strouhal number.
t	Time.
t_0	Reference time.
U	Channel inlet mean velocity.
u,v	Velocity components.
U_j	Jet inlet mean velocity.
VS	Vortex shedding.
Y	Dimensionless mixing quantity.
x,y,z	Cartesian coordinates.

Abbreviations

ADE	Alternating Direction Explicit.
ADI	Alternating Direction Implicit.
CFL	Courant-Friedrich-Lewy number.
GCI	Grid Convergence Index.

Subscripts

max	Maximum value.
pp	Peak-to-peak value.
t	Partial derivative in time t .
x, xx	First and second partial derivatives in x .
$x = a$	$x = a$ location.
$xx0$	Finite difference approximation of the second derivative in x with null first derivative.
y, yy	First and second partial derivatives in y .
$yy0$	Finite difference approximation of the second derivative in y with null first derivative.
i,j	Nodal location.

Greek Symbols

Δ	Magnitude difference.
η	Mixing efficiency [%].
μ	Dynamic viscosity.
∇^2	Laplace operator.
ω	Vorticity component in z coordinate.
Π	Pumping power.
ψ	Dimensionless streamfunction.
ρ	Density.
σ	Standard deviation.
$\vec{\Omega}$	Vorticity vector.
$\vec{\Psi}$	Potential vector.

Superscripts

in	Position at the inlet.
n	Iteration number.
2_{wall}	Wall surface position
$\hat{\quad}$	Dimensional magnitude (SI units).

1. Introduction

Heat and mass transfer is a frequent requirement in applications such as heat exchangers [1] and combustion engines [2] in mechanical engineering, aircraft and rocket jets [3] in aeronautical engineering, chemical synthesis [4] in chemical engineering, or microfluid-based Lab-On-Chip devices for disease diagnosis [5] in biomedical engineering, amongst many others. In these engineering applications, fluid mixing may play a critical role, which generates considerable interest in achieving high mixing efficiency [1]. The mixing efficiency term η is one of the most important aspects in the present manuscript, since this parameter is a measure of how well fluids are mixed. A perfect mix ($\eta = 100\%$) at the outlet means that the mixing device achieved the maximum efficiency.

Traditionally, researchers have classified devices for mixing of fluids into a passive and active devices [6]. Active devices include moving elements that enhance mixing, and can actually deploy a wider range of control options by varying the frequency of motion of an active element. However, they have the drawbacks of requiring additional power consumption, increase complexity in the design, and require maintenance. Additionally, if the device is intended at microscale, the deployment of tiny stepwise motors may not be feasible. All these inconveniences are not present in passive devices. For these, usually obstacles are aggregated to the channels to promote mixing at zero cost (except when drag forces must be overcome thus increasing pumping power). In terms of scaling up, the use of passive devices is attractive at reduced scale because of the said drawbacks in active devices. Thus, a good advantage of the passive mixer is that fluid mechanics will work similarly even if scaled-up from micro to macroscale. Nevertheless, at nanoscale the present continuum mechanics will not be applicable and mixing mechanics may not respect the present results [7]. Although the mixing device can be scaled-up from micro to macroscale in terms of fluid mechanics, the specific application will also play an important role on the overall performance. There are certain disciplines where efficient scale-up may not be easy, such as industrial production

29 of biodiesel [8], because of larger channel sections influence axial dispersion of bulk phase
30 components and methanol phase; polymer manufacturing [9], as a result of scaling-up
31 of involved chemical reactions as well; or carbon fiber manufacturing [10], due to high
32 costs attributed to gas mixing and release in manufacturing furnaces.

33 In terms of design of a passive mixing machine, the most popular application is to
34 use different channel shapes (T-shaped, F-shaped, zig-zag, etc.) or to place objects at
35 the walls as mixing promoters. In [11] a T-shaped channel was used to mix two fluids at
36 different temperature and low Reynolds. In [12] F-shaped units were used to enhance
37 mixing, yielding improved mixing with respect to the T-shaped channel. In [13], Y-
38 shaped and complex shaped channels were tested numerically and experimentally for
39 mixing, achieving an important enhancement in mixing. An important limitation in
40 “shaped” mixers (T-shaped, F-shaped, etc.) is that the pumping power cost is highly
41 increased in comparison to straight channels [14, 15]. As said, to place objects in the
42 channels is another way to enhance mixing. Examples of this approach can be found
43 extensively in the literature. For instance, in [16] two bars were placed as mixing unit in
44 a microchannel to enhance low-Reynolds mixing. An optimisation study was carried out
45 to find the best angles for the bars to decrease the pumping power and maximise mixing.
46 Similarly, Tayeb et al. [17] tested square-shaped protuberances in a zig-zag fashion to
47 promote mixing between two shear-thinning non-Newtonian fluids. In addition, other
48 chaotic shapes were tested to achieve more energetically efficient mixing. Tseng et al.
49 [18] also tested the combination of diamond-shaped pillars with adjacent square-shaped
50 protuberances for laminar mixing. They used such configuration to promote vorticity
51 and generate secondary flows in spanwise planes. Although to promote mixing by
52 using objects or obstacles is interesting, it suffers from increasing pumping power if
53 the placement of elements slowdown the flow notably, as observed in the aforesaid
54 investigations.

55 Another efficient option to enhance mixing by a passive method is to use vortex
56 shedding. One of the side effects of this approach is that the detached vortical structures
57 have the capability to enhance mixing if the object is placed suitably. Examples of

58 success can be found in [1, 19], where a rectangular pillar is placed in the centreline of a
59 microchannel. Since two inlet laminar flows at different temperature/mass fraction are
60 entering the microchannel, the centreline also coincides with their separation in the inlet
61 and the pillar object is placed to split both flows. Due to the collision with the pillar,
62 above a critical Reynolds number (which is fully dependent on the geometry of the
63 channel, pillar and flow regime), vortex shedding structures appear and these promote
64 thermal/molecular mixing between the two flows. This phenomenon is important and
65 can be actually predicted by means of Machine Learning methods on this geometries,
66 as done in [20]. Despite geometries of short aspect ratio pillars have been studied in
67 the literature as said, the impact of very large aspect ratios leading to vortex shedding
68 for mixing has not been investigated. When the aspect ratio is as long as the flow can
69 be fully developed on top and bottom of the pillar object, this situation can be also
70 interpreted as the mixing between two parallel fully-developed channel flows discharging
71 into a large channel, or two laminar wall jet mixing. Due to the geometry and flow
72 regime conditions, the flow is detached at the end of the split channels, and may lead
73 to vortex shedding structures.

74 Although the investigation on vortex shedding mechanics has been in continuous
75 development since a century ago, this is still a topic of high interest nowadays. There
76 are many researchers that investigated recently relevant characteristics of the mechanics
77 of the oscillatory motion of detached flows. For instance [21] developed an experimental
78 work on vortex shedding at subcritical regime using Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV)
79 and pressure surface measurements. In such research was observed that the early sep-
80 aration of flow led to larger downstream wakes. Important modes of oscillation were
81 identified as well, with Proper Orthogonal Decomposition techniques (POD) on the
82 pressure fluctuation data, which explained the most relevant vortex shedding charac-
83 teristics. Some authors also tested the effect on vortex shedding due to the aggregation
84 of fins and other elements, as in [22]. In this work was tested experimentally the effect
85 on vortex shedding of adding fins to a circular cylinder, observing certain control on
86 the recirculation behind the body. Other authors in the literature, as e.g. [23] studied

87 laminar flows passing through arrays of elements, to predict the transitional behaviour
88 of the flow as a function of the density of object pins. In this work was studied how
89 the density of pins can control the transition to unsteady flows, since relations between
90 the critical Reynolds number and the Roshko number with the density of pins were
91 found. For heat transfer enhancement, in [24] the laminar flow-induced vibration of a
92 D-section cylinder confined in a channel is studied numerically. An oscillatory motion
93 of the downstream flow takes place due to the intensification promoted by the galloping
94 motion of the object, enhancing heat transfer notably but under complexity due to the
95 moving object. A very similar problem was also studied in [25], but oriented to harvest
96 the energy from the dynamic combination of vortex-induced vibration and galloping
97 motion.

98 Confined vortex shedding is an example of application where ground effects are im-
99 portant in the characteristic flow mechanics. Several researchers have investigated the
100 effect of ground or walls on the development of the vortical structures. For instance in
101 [26] an oscillatory flow detached from a flat plate was analysed numerically. This work
102 demonstrated that the spacing between the flat plate and the ground wall highly affects
103 the detached flow. As the gap between the flat plate and the ground was decreased, the
104 strength of the vortex shedding was decreased, which is consistent with experimental
105 data. An interesting experimental study on confined vortex shedding was developed
106 in [27], where the shape of objects, effect of blockage ratio and Reynolds number was
107 assessed. The analysis concluded that the size of the spacing between the walls and
108 the object was the most influential aspect, which was able to activate/deactivate the
109 unsteady oscillatory mechanics of the flow. In [1, 28] vortex shedding past a confined
110 square cylinder was promoted and boosted to enhance mixing between two fluids, simi-
111 larly to the objective in the present manuscript. The oscillatory motion was found very
112 influenced (and predictable [20]) by proper combination between the blockage ratio, as-
113 pect ratio and Reynolds number. More comments on the relevant effect of the blockage
114 ratio and other geometric parameters in the behaviour of the downstream confined flows
115 can be found in other recent works in the literature [29, 30, 31, 32]. This activation of

116 confined vortex shedding is the objective of the present work to enhance mixing.

117 To the knowledge of the authors, there is no literature on the use of laminar wall
118 jets for thermal/mass mixing enhancement. Laminar mixing is specially difficult, since
119 there is no turbulence aiding the mixing process as in other heat/mass applications
120 with turbulent jets [33, 34]. The motivation to study a laminar mixing device instead
121 of a turbulent mixing is that some applications do not deal with flows at enough speed
122 to involve turbulence. A good example is the biomedical engineering field. For in-
123 stance, when the fluid to be mixed is blood, turbulence is avoided as much as possible.
124 Turbulence in blood can lead to important complications for the pathophysiology of
125 the vascular system, including mechanical hemolysis (destruction of red blood cells,
126 releasing their content into the blood stream flow) [35]. Another application is the
127 administration of vaccines. Some vaccines such as Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 Vaccine
128 requires mechanical mixing with a diluent by a trained nurse [36]. This process is car-
129 ried out manually by inverting the recipient twenty times (10+10). This must be done
130 gently to avoid shaking [37], thus this process can be done efficiently by a mechanical
131 mixer using wall jets. As the flow is not impinging on objects or obstacles, the wall
132 jet mixing device is a novel recommendation for nearly any sensitive laminar fluid .
133 The only work found that considered a wall jet configuration is [38], who developed a
134 single simulation of a wall jet (their work was more focused on twin jets), not extracting
135 any feedback on design modifications. In their work, two laminar twin jets in a semi-
136 confined space were simulated in a 2D computational domain. They tested different
137 positions of the twin jets, until they achieved a wall jet case scenario. They found out
138 that the best mixing with ambient flow took place for the wall jet, what encouraged
139 the present work.

140 Apart from [38], the most related studies to this topic in the literature are those
141 that investigate mixing/instabilities between twin free/semi-confined jets, but these
142 do not evaluate heat or mass transfer. However, Nahum and Seifert [39] suggested
143 years ago the use of twin jets as mixing improvement in micromixing applications and
144 studied numerically and experimentally in detail confined twin jet instabilities, as well

145 as the use of harmonic excitation to enhance mixing. In [40] the self-oscillatory motion
146 of confined turbulent twin jets from round and squared cross sections was analysed
147 in detail numerically. In this study it was observed that if the spacing between jets
148 is not large (lower than four times the diameter), the two jets merge downstream
149 and behave like a single oscillatory jet. Such oscillation is due to the formation of
150 vortical structures suffering expansion, elongation, and contraction. When the spacing
151 is increased, the jets oscillate individually. However, it is interesting the observation
152 that when the spacing is increased, the oscillation frequency is not significantly affected.
153 Oscillatory characteristics of dual jets were also analysed in [41], where an experimental
154 study on two jets are entering into a dome-shape mixing chamber was developed. The
155 oscillatory motion was controlled mainly by the flow rate and complex vorticity patterns
156 are observed inside the mixing dome. Some studies on turbulent jet mixing such as [42]
157 just consider a wall jet in tandem with a free jet (parallel offset jet), thus the mixing
158 is not constrained to a channel geometry. In their study they studied experimentally
159 both jets at $Re = 10^4$ and found vortex shedding-like structures in the shear layer
160 interaction similar to those detached from a bluff body; opposite to the free jet only
161 scenario in which Kelvin-Helmholtz instabilities dominate along the shear layer. In [43]
162 the interaction of a wall jet and an offset jet is also studied but numerically. In their
163 work they varied gradually the ratio of the mean velocity of these jets and studied
164 different turbulence models. Another investigation on the interaction between an offset
165 jet and a wall jet can be found in [44]. In this work, the interaction of these jets is
166 analysed numerically, and they observed again a very strong impact of the offset ratio
167 on the development of the flow structures. There are also few applications of confined
168 (or semi-confined) twin jets. In [45], 2D simulations of three laminar twin jets in a semi-
169 confined channel were developed. Jet mixing is studied focused on the critical Reynolds
170 above which the problem becomes transient and thus mixing is enhanced. The author
171 concluded that for the three-jet device the flow could be stable&symmetric (with low
172 Reynolds), unstable&symmetric (with moderate Reynolds), and unstable&asymmetric
173 (with high Reynolds). Recently, some authors also tested the use of confined jets in

174 thermal mixing. For instance, in [46] two turbulent parallel confined jets at different
175 temperature are passing thorough perforated obstacles (porous surfaces) at a certain
176 distance to study numerically and experimentally the influence on thermal mixing.
177 They observed that despite the obstacles have a positive impact on mixing, turbulence
178 is reduced downstream. A very similar and recent work was developed in [47], where the
179 authors tested the improvement in thermal mixing of confined turbulent twin jets by
180 placing cylindrical obstacles at a certain distance. The mixing efficiency was improved
181 with this method by testing numerically and experimentally the use of different row
182 of obstacles. In [48], Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are trained with experimental
183 data from the thermal mixing between two turbulent twin jets in a cross-section narrow
184 channel. In this work several design parameters were taken into account (jet inclination,
185 temperature difference, jet flow ratio, jet diameters), which once input to the ANN
186 model, the thermal output can be predicted.

187 All the aforementioned works strongly motivated the application of parallel wall
188 jet flows in a channel for our thermal/mass transfer applications, since the interesting
189 interaction between the shear layers of both flows is worthy of investigation. The most
190 important novelty in the present work is that we aim to design a novel laminar wall
191 jet mixer, by testing geometric and flow regime variations, with a special interest in
192 boosting vortex shedding to enhance mixing. Since this design is oriented to improve
193 the state-of-the-art in scalable micromixing, we also pay attention to obtain a device
194 with low pumping power and high mixing efficiency.

195 Regarding the numerical code used in this work, the non-uniform finite difference
196 approach [49] has been successfully applied to other previous works in the literature,
197 such as sudden expansions [50] or vertical pipe flow instability analysis [51]. However,
198 the method has not been applied to thermal or molecular mixing of flows before. The
199 most popular approach in the literature of mixing is the use of finite volume [1] or
200 finite element methods [52]. With respect to the use of non-uniform grids in general
201 CFD applications, some authors have developed recently hybrid approaches such as
202 the hybrid finite difference-finite volume schemes [53], which benefits of the higher

203 order convergence property of finite difference methods and the conservativeness of
204 finite volume methods when applied on a non-uniform mesh. Nevertheless, this method
205 is useful only if there is an abrupt change in the flow, since for areas of uniformity,
206 the computational costs are unnecessarily increased. In [54] the use of a high-order
207 unconditionally stable Alternating Direction Explicit (ADE) scheme is proposed to
208 solve the stability and efficiency problems on non-uniform grids that takes place in the
209 standard ADE scheme. This method allows to solve the fluid diffusion equation on
210 non-uniform grids by means of a fourth-order finite difference approximation, achieving
211 important reduction in elapsed time of computations. The method has been applied
212 in [55]. The present work uses a similar approach to ADE, which is the Alternating
213 Direction Implicit (ADI) scheme [50]. Thus, to use a non-uniform finite difference
214 approach provides some advantages, such as the possibility to implement an in-house
215 numerical code, which is simpler to code than finite element/volume methods, and
216 has the advantages of saving computational resources as a consequence of the adaptive
217 non-uniform meshes. The use of finite difference is also advantageous for this specific
218 geometry, since the domain is fully rectangular so the grid is rectangular as well and
219 the method is very efficient in solving the governing partial differential equations. The
220 use of a non-uniform nodal distribution also provides the advantage of avoiding the use
221 of immersed boundary conditions, in addition to the advantages in stability, accuracy
222 and simplicity of using a Cartesian grids [49]. For complex domains, finite element
223 or finite volume methods are usually preferred over finite difference schemes, as their
224 integral formulation does not have a priori any mesh structure preference [56]. In the
225 present investigation it is demonstrated that the in-house code is a useful approach to
226 evaluate and analyse thermal/molecular mixing of flows. In addition, whilst the use of
227 commercial softwares is acceptable in many scenarios, CFD practitioners do often write
228 their own codes in order to include or develop new approaches or modules. Moreover,
229 there are strong limitations in commercial softwares to deploy intrusive features such
230 as, for instance, optimisation methods or intrusive uncertainty quantification methods
231 [57, 58].

232 The paper is divided into the following sections. Section 2 introduces the geometry
 233 of the mixing device, as well as the governing equations and the numerical approach
 234 carried out, which includes also validation of numerical results. Section 3 is dedicated
 235 to the discussion of the results. Finally, Section 4 summarises the conclusions from this
 236 investigation.

237 2. Governing Equations and Numerical Approach

238 The geometry under study is shown in Fig. 1. It consist of a 2D channel with
 239 two incompressible fluids which comes in from the left side. A mass flow rate \hat{q}_j of
 240 a fluid 1, with a solute concentration (or a temperature, if the application is heat
 241 transfer) of value \hat{C}_0 , comes into the channel through its lower half. Additionally,
 242 another and identical mass flow rate \hat{q}_j of a fluid 2, which is solute free (or it has a
 243 different temperature if heat transfer is considered), enters through the upper half of
 244 the channel. Both fluids have the same density $\hat{\rho}$ and viscosity $\hat{\mu}$. If mass transfer
 245 is considered, this assumption is correct. However, for heat transfer, since density
 246 and viscosity is temperature dependent, this would be only correct if the temperature
 247 difference between fluids 1 and 2 does not lead to sensitive differences between the
 248 properties of these flows. The channel is \hat{H} meters wide, \hat{L} meters long, and has a solid
 249 separation between inlets, so that \hat{h} is the wall jet width. Defining \hat{U}_j as the mean
 250 upper and bottom inlet velocities, the mass flow rates \hat{q}_j can be written as

$$\hat{q}_j = \hat{U}_j \hat{h}, \quad (1)$$

251 so the total mass flow rate through the channel is

$$\hat{q}_j + \hat{q}_j = 2\hat{q}_j = \hat{q} = \hat{U} \hat{H}, \quad (2)$$

252 where U is the mean velocity at the channel exit.

253 Defining the dimensionless parameters $L \equiv \hat{L}/\hat{H}$ and $h \equiv \hat{h}/\hat{H}$, we have then for
 254 the velocities $\hat{U}_j = \frac{\hat{q}_j}{\hat{h}} = \frac{\hat{U} \hat{H}}{2\hat{h}} = \frac{\hat{U}}{2h}$. We shall also define the dimensionless distance
 255 $h' \equiv 1 - h$, which is the distance from the channel lower side to the pillar upper one.

Figure 1: Sketch of the geometry of the two parallel wall jets (represented by blue and red velocity profiles). The area shadowed in gray is the computational domain.

256 In this study, both wall jets are fully developed Hagen-Poiseuille flows. This assumption
 257 allows to reduce the computational domain to a rectangular region downstream the
 258 inlets, i.e. the shaded region of Fig. 1, with perfectly identified boundary conditions
 259 for the two jets that enter the computational domain above and below the pillar, as
 260 shown in Fig. 1.

261 By using as characteristic magnitudes \hat{U} , \hat{H} and \hat{H}/\hat{U} to make dimensionless ve-
 262 locity, length and time, respectively (in Cartesian coordinates (x, y, z)), the stream
 263 function-vorticity $(\psi - \omega)$ formulation [59, 60] will be used to solve the 2D incompress-
 264 ible flow on the (x, y) plane. Firstly, the velocity components are related to the stream
 265 function as:

$$\vec{v} = (u, v, 0) = \nabla \wedge \vec{\Psi} = \nabla \wedge (0, 0, \psi) = (\psi_y, -\psi_x, 0), \quad (3)$$

266 where the subscripts x and y denote the partial derivatives in x and y , respectively.
 267 Secondly, by means of the definition of the vorticity $\vec{\Omega}$ one has

$$\vec{\Omega} = \nabla \wedge \vec{v} = (0, 0, v_x - u_y) = (0, 0, \omega). \quad (4)$$

268 Thirdly, by combining both equations, one can obtain

$$-\omega = \psi_{xx} + \psi_{yy}, \quad (5)$$

269 where the double subscript means second order partial derivative. Finally, from the
 270 z -coordinate of the transport equation of the vorticity $\vec{\Omega}$, it yields

$$\omega_t + \psi_y \omega_x - \psi_x \omega_y = \frac{\omega_{xx} + \omega_{yy}}{Re}, \quad (6)$$

271 where Re is the Reynolds number $Re = \frac{\hat{\rho}\hat{U}\hat{H}}{\hat{\mu}}$ (which can be also written as $Re = \frac{\hat{\rho}2\hat{U}_j\hat{h}}{\hat{\mu}}$
 272 to make it based on jet characteristics), and all subscripts denote partial derivatives.
 273 Equations (5) and (6) are a system to solve both components of the velocity but not the
 274 pressure field, since it does not appear in the mathematical formulation of the problem.
 275 The corresponding boundary conditions to solve Equations (5)–(6) are described in
 276 Appendix A.

277 Both fluids, which enter into the channel through the left hand side, will be mixed
 278 downstream. If \hat{C} is defined as the solute concentration of the fluid in any position,
 279 by using \hat{C}_0 to make \hat{C} dimensionless, one can then define $Y = \hat{C}/\hat{C}_0$, which is called
 280 dimensionless mixing quantity in this work. This quantity would be the dimensionless
 281 mass fraction of the fluid in a mass transfer problem, or dimensionless temperature in
 282 a heat transfer application with two fluids at different temperature. Since the most
 283 important quantity of interest is the mixing efficiency, in order to know how the dimen-
 284 sionless scalar magnitude Y evolves along the channel the convection-diffusion equation
 285 governing the process can be written as [61, 62]:

$$Y_t + \psi_y Y_x - \psi_x Y_y = \frac{Y_{zz} + Y_{yy}}{Pe}, \quad (7)$$

286 where $Pe = \frac{\hat{U}\hat{H}}{\hat{D}}$ ($= \frac{2\hat{U}_j\hat{h}}{\hat{D}}$) is the Peclet-like number, with \hat{D} the molecular diffusivity
 287 (in mass transfer) or thermal diffusivity (in heat transfer). The corresponding boundary
 288 conditions to solve Equation (7) are described in Appendix B.

289 As aforesaid, the pressure field is not explicitly solved in the mathematical formu-
 290 lation. If one is interested in solving also the dimensionless pressure field p once ψ ,
 291 w and Y are known, then the corresponding Poisson equation for p (derived from the
 292 divergence of the momentum equation) must be solved. In terms of primitive variables,
 293 this is [63, 64]:

$$\nabla^2 p = -2(v_x u_y - u_x v_y), \quad (8)$$

294 whilst in terms of ψ , it can be written as

$$\nabla^2 p = 2(\psi_{xx}\psi_{yy} - \psi_{xy}^2). \quad (9)$$

Figure 2: Nodal distribution with $Nx = 200$, $Ny = 70$ ($ny_1 = 25$, $ny_2 = 20$) for $L = 12$ and $h = 0.4$. The nodes are clustered in the central part of the microchannel, as this is the main mixing contact area. There is also more compression in the walls, to properly solve the boundary layer.

295 The corresponding boundary conditions to solve Equation (9) are described in Appendix C.

296 The oscillatory behaviour of any magnitude, say g , at the channel outlet because
 297 of the development of a downstream oscillatory flow (which will depend on Re and h),
 298 will be characterised by its frequency of oscillation \hat{f} . This frequency is represented in
 299 dimensionless notation by means of the Strouhal number: $St = \hat{f}\hat{H}/\hat{U}$. In this case,
 300 its time-averaged value during an oscillation period St^{-1} can be computed as

$$\langle g \rangle = \frac{1}{St^{-1}} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+St^{-1}} g(t') dt', \quad (10)$$

301 being t_0 any dimensionless time reference for the periodic flow.

302 Pressure losses are an important aspect in flows through pipes or channels. This
 303 parameter defines the pumping power required for the fluid to flow along the duct.
 304 Concretely, this is the power needed to maintain a given flow rate \hat{q} along the channel,
 305 for which the pressure and viscous losses must be overcome (which can be evaluated as
 306 the inlet-outlet pressure difference times the mass flow rate). Thence, the dimensionless

307 pumping power, denoted by Π , can be evaluated as

$$\Pi = \frac{\langle \Delta \hat{p} \rangle \hat{q}}{\hat{\rho} \hat{U}^3 \hat{H}}, \quad (11)$$

308 where $\Delta \hat{p}$ is the dimensional pressure drop between the channel inlet and outlet. Due
 309 to the chosen characteristic magnitudes, finally the pumping power can be written as

$$\Pi = \frac{\langle \Delta \hat{p} \rangle}{\hat{\rho} \hat{U}^2} = \langle \Delta p \rangle, \quad (12)$$

310 which means that the inlet pumping power is governed by the dimensionless pressure
 311 drop along the channel.

312 Finally, the most important parameter in the design of the device is the assessment of
 313 the mixing quality at the channel outlet. This feature is defined as the mixing efficiency
 314 η , in %. According to previous works (e.g. [65, 62, 1]), this quantity of interest can be
 315 written as:

$$\eta = \left(1 - \frac{\langle \sigma \rangle}{\sigma_{max}} \right) \times 100, \quad (13)$$

316 where σ is the standard deviation of the corresponding scalar magnitude at the channel
 317 exit, and σ_{max} is the maximum standard deviation at the inlet (which is a 0.5 in the
 318 present two fluids mixing problem). Due to the fact that $0 \leq Y \leq 1$, then $0 \leq \sigma \leq 0.5$,
 319 where $\sigma = 0$ means uniform distribution of Y at the outlet with full mixing ($\eta = 100\%$);
 320 whereas $\sigma = 0.5$ would mean a very poor mixing ($\eta = 0\%$). Due to the fact that
 321 the efficiency η can be evaluated at any longitudinal location x and not just only at
 322 the outlet, the subscript $x = a$, with a being the corresponding coordinate, in $\eta_{x=a}$
 323 indicates the location where the efficiency is evaluated, unless evaluated at the outlet
 324 (no subscript). This will allow us to assess how the channel performs, i.e. how the
 325 efficiency increases, from a till the outlet. This shows the benefits of increasing the
 326 length of the channel. To that end, the efficiency difference will be defined as

$$\Delta \eta = \eta - \eta_{x=a}. \quad (14)$$

327 Another important parameter to assess the goodness of each mixing device is the
 328 relation between the required pumping power and the mixing efficiency. This is the

329 so-called mixing energy cost *mec*, which is defined as [66]

$$mec = \frac{\Pi}{\eta}. \quad (15)$$

330 This quantity is a measure of the required energy per each percentage unit of mixing
331 achieved.

332 The present work is focused on the investigation of different configurations of wall
333 jets to enhance mixing thanks to vortex shedding mechanics. In order to clearly differ-
334 entiate the impact of geometry from other contributions such as variations in the fluid
335 properties, phases, etc., the complexity of the problem in terms of cross-effect contribu-
336 tions has been kept simple. This does not mean at all that more complex applications
337 are unfeasible. Actually, these are encouraged.

338 In terms of fluid properties, the present study is extensible to any viscosity and den-
339 sity fluid. Moreover, if the fluid is non-Newtonian, viscosity can be input as a function
340 easily. Must be recall that if density and viscosity do change, these parameters are part
341 of the Reynolds number definition. Therefore, if the Reynolds and Peclet-like numbers
342 are constant, the outcome does not change. The Reynolds number also involves flow
343 velocity. Thus, as long as compressible effects are not present (e.g. shocks at high-
344 speed), any velocity profile and magnitude can be imposed at the inlet. Temperature
345 is another interesting parameter. The present study considers either an isolated heat
346 transfer problem or mass transfer problem, in order to facilitate the understanding of
347 the impact of the wall jet geometry in mixing. Including cross-effects would affect
348 mixing, thus wrong conclusions may be extracted. For instance, when studying mass
349 transfer, locations of high/low temperature would vary molecular diffusivity, and the
350 impact of wall jets on mixing may not be that clear. Finally, multiphase simulation is
351 also another interesting possibility for problems involving more than one phase. The
352 present investigation is a single-phase simulation, but for multiphase problems the nu-
353 merical approach would still be valid. Unfortunately, computational resources would
354 be more demanding: for multiphase modelling one should select and code a specific
355 modelling: Eulerian model, Volume of Fluid (VOF) model, etc. Although this can be

356 implemented onto the present code, this would not be straightforward. For a successful
357 implementation of the streamfunction-vorticity formulation in a multiphase flow, see for
358 instance [67]. As final conclusion, it is remarked that all the discussed features can be
359 combined at once into the simulation, in order to predict the performance of more com-
360 plex mixing applications using wall jets. The only “limitation” that one may encounter
361 in the customisation of the simulation is the imposition of inlet pressure. Unfortunately,
362 the streamfunction-vorticity formulation does not allow to impose pressure boundary
363 conditions. The pressure field is solved at a final stage once the velocity field is obtained
364 and the pressure at inlet is adapted to the one needed to get the corresponding flow.

365 2.1. Numerical Details

366 A non-uniform mesh [49] with mesh nodes clustered close to the inlets and side
367 walls has been used. The transient set of Equations (5)-(7) has been solved by means
368 of finite difference-based numerical scheme [49], where central second order spatial finite
369 difference approximations have been used for spatial partial derivatives. Regarding the
370 temporal terms of the equations, these have been discretised with a central first order
371 scheme. Therefore, if Equation (6) (and similarly Equation (7)), is discretised in an
372 arbitrary mesh node (i, j) and time instant n , it is obtained:

$$\omega_t|_{i,j}^n + \psi_y|_{i,j}^n \omega_x|_{i,j}^n - \psi_x \omega_y|_{i,j}^n = \frac{\omega_{xx}|_{i,j}^n + \omega_{yy}|_{i,j}^n}{Re}, \quad (16)$$

373 from which the explicit equation for the interior unknowns $\omega|_{i,j}^{n+1}$ can be obtained by

$$\omega|_{i,j}^{n+1} = \omega|_{i,j}^n + \Delta t (NLT|_{i,j}^n + VIS|_{i,j}^n), \quad (17)$$

374 where NLT and VIS stand for the discretisation of the Non Lineal Terms and Viscous
375 ones, respectively. Starting from an initial solution ψ^0 , ω^0 and Y^0 (the whole domain
376 is initialised with $Y^0 = 0$, as well as $\psi^0 = \psi^{in}$ and $\omega^0 = \omega^{in}$, whose values are defined
377 in Appendix A), Equation (17) (and the equivalent for Y) allows to advance in time
378 ω (and Y) from $n = 0$ to $n = 1$. After that, the discretisation of Equation (5) with
379 second order spatial finite difference approximations in $|_{i,j}^{n+1}$ is

$$\psi_{xx}|_{i,j}^{n+1} + \psi_{yy}|_{i,j}^{n+1} = -\omega|_{i,j}^{n+1}. \quad (18)$$

380 This allows, by solving the corresponding highly sparse set of equations, to solve the
381 unknowns of ψ at each interior node. Then, the boundary conditions are updated at
382 the next time step by means of the expressions given in Equations (A.2)–(A.5). This
383 three-step scheme consists of knowing: i) ω^{n+1} and Y^{n+1} on the interior points; ii) ψ^{n+1}
384 on the interior points; and iii) ω^{n+1} , ψ^{n+1} and Y^{n+1} on the boundaries. Such scheme is
385 repeated iteratively until the flow reaches a steady or periodic (oscillatory) behaviour.

386 2.2. Validation

387 To validate the abovementioned methodology, three 2D problems with analytical
388 solutions and a fourth comparison with data from literature have been solved. The first
389 validation test case aims to check if the fully developed 2D Poiseuille flow is kept along
390 a straight channel when this solution is used as initial condition, as it is depicted in
391 Fig. 3(a). A parabolic x -velocity profile with null y -velocity

$$\vec{v} = (u, 0, 0) = (6y(1 - y), 0, 0), \quad (19)$$

392 is imposed onto the inlet of the geometry by means of ψ and w as

$$\psi = 6(y^2/2 - y^3/3), w = 6(1 - 2y). \quad (20)$$

393 The results at the outlet, in terms of both primitive and non-primitive variables, are
394 shown in Fig. 4. The absolute error with respect to the theoretical profile is also shown.
395 As can be seen, the agreement with the expected solution is very good. Additionally,
396 the solution given by the Poisson pressure in Equation (9) has been compared with the
397 theoretical pressure drop $\Delta p = 12L/Re$. This comparison is shown in Fig. 4(e), where
398 a very good agreement can be observed for the range of Reynolds numbers under study.

399 The second validation test case is dedicated to check the development of the parabolic
400 Poiseuille x -velocity profile from a uniform profile. To that end, the geometry and
401 boundary conditions shown in Fig. 3(b) are numerically simulated. In the figure is
402 depicted that there is a very short piece of channel upstream (end marked with two
403 black points at the channel walls) with constant uniform x -velocity $u = 1$. This is so

Figure 3: Sketch of the geometries and boundary conditions used in the validation step. Parabolic and uniform axial inlet profiles have been simulated: (a) 2D Poiseuille flow under constant pressure gradient; (b) Development of a 2D Poiseuille flow; (c) Convection-diffusion of a scalar magnitude in a uniform flow with translational moving walls in the axial direction.

404 because this facilitates to the flow to adapt to the computational domain. The size
 405 of the small portion of the channel with imposed uniform velocity is for the fluid to
 406 progressively adapt to the no-slip wall. If the length L of the channel is long enough, a
 407 fully developed Poiseuille flow will exit the channel at the outlet, as can be seen in Fig.
 408 5, where the streamlines and vorticity contour are plotted for the two channel lengths
 409 used. Fig. 5(c)-(d) show that close to the exit, the streamlines and vorticity contours
 410 are almost horizontal, which evidences that a fully developed flow has been reached.
 411 This, however, does not happen in the shorter channel in Fig. 5(a)-(b). This can be
 412 validated by comparing the fluid properties at the outlet with the theoretical/fully de-
 413 veloped ones. This is shown in Fig. 6, where the primitives and non-primitives variables
 414 at the outlet are compared. One can see that the the longer the channel, the better the

Figure 4: Validation of CFD simulations with theoretical data: (a) and (b) validation by means of primitive variables; (c) and (d) by means of non-primitive variables; (e) validation of computational channel pressure drop. In each subfigure the top plots correspond to the validation, and the bottom plots are the numerical absolute error. The markers correspond to theoretical data and the solid lines are numerical results.

Figure 5: Non-primitive variables contours for the second validation test and two different channel lengths: (a)-(b) for $L = 5$; and (c)-(d) for $L = 15$. (a) and (c) are streamlines, and (b) and (d) isolines of vorticity ω . It can be observed that the initial uniform profile is transformed into a parabolic profile as the flow develops. The initial uniform flow is kept until $x = 1$ due to a small portion of pipe is artificially modelled as moving at the same velocity to facilitate the adaption of the flow. The area of highest vorticity takes place around $x = 1$ also for this reason.

415 agreement with the theoretical profiles.

416 The third validation test case is dedicated to validate the computational approach
 417 when the convection-diffusion equation is solved coupled with the flow motion. To
 418 that end, the problem shown in Fig. 3(c) is studied: a uniform flow enters a channel
 419 where both side walls are moving at the same velocity too. Under these conditions,
 420 the solution at any point of the domain in terms of primitive variables is $\vec{v} = (1, 0, 0)$.

Figure 6: Comparison of the (fully developed) velocity profiles at the outlet for the second validation test and the different channel lengths: (a) for primitive variables; and (b) for non-primitive variables. The marker data corresponds to theoretical data, and the solid lines are numerical data. As the channel length is increased, the discrepancy between the theoretical fully developed flow data and numerical data is reduced as expected.

421 Taking this into account in Equation (7), the steady state simplifies to

$$0 = \frac{Y_{zz} + Y_{yy}}{Pe}. \quad (21)$$

422 With the boundary conditions in Equations (B.2)-(B.5), Equation (21) can be solved
423 by separation of variables, obtaining [61]:

$$Y(x,y) = \frac{2}{\pi} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(k\alpha\pi)}{k} \cos(k\pi y) \exp\left(-\frac{2k^2\pi^2}{Pe + \sqrt{Pe^2 + 4k^2\pi^2}}x\right) + \gamma \quad (22)$$

424 where $\gamma = q_1/(q_1 + q_2)$ is the ratio of the upper half flow rate to the total one. For
425 $U = \text{constant}$ and $\gamma = 0.5$, the comparison of the CFD solution and Equation (22) is
426 shown in Fig. 7, where x and y profiles of Y are compared for two Peclet-like numbers.
427 As shown, the agreement is excellent.

428 Finally, a fourth validation test case is run with the CFD code. The simulation
429 corresponds to the streamlines of a wall jet problem studied in Rafferty and Kaminski
430 [38], likewise validated with three different sources from the literature. The configura-
431 tion of the geometry (according to the notation used in the present paper) is $h = 0.05$

Figure 7: Comparison between numerical and analytical solutions of Y for the indicated Peclet-like numbers at different x and y positions: (a) profiles along y coordinate at $x = 5$; and (b) profiles along x coordinate at $y = 1$.

432 and channel length $L = 30/4$. The Reynolds number under study, according with our
 433 definition, is $Re = 70$, and the inlet velocity of the jets are uniform velocity profile. The
 434 comparison between our numerical results and those reported in Rafferty and Kaminski
 435 ski [38] is shown in Fig. 8. The results show almost no difference between each figure,
 436 concluding with this tested case the validation of the numerical procedure.

Figure 8: Validation of streamlines with data reported in Rafferty and Kaminski [38] (subfigure (a) reproduced with permission). Subfigure (b) is the current numerical simulation of the streamlines.

437 2.3. Grid Convergence Study

438 Instead of using a generic and unique mesh for all geometric configurations under
439 study, a detailed grid convergence study has been carried out for the three different
440 values of h of this study: $h = (0.1, 0.2, 0.4)$. Thanks to the Grid Convergence Index
441 GCI [68], an optimal number of nodes has been identified for ny_1 , ny_2 and Nx (see Fig.
442 2). Regarding the input parameters, the most unfavourable situation with $Re = 200$
443 and $Pe = 200$ has been analysed. This provides a robust measure of confidence on the
444 optimal mesh. Once the geometric configuration is selected, at least three values are
445 given for the number of nodes in a specific region, while the other two remains constant,
446 in order to find an adequate number of nodes that allows to perform the simulation
447 at higher accuracy but lower computational cost. The magnitude analysed during the
448 GCI procedure was the mixing efficiency η at the outlet.

449 To start with, the top and bottom inlet mesh with $h = 0.4$ will be analysed first.
450 Initially, with fixed values of $ny_2 = 20$ and $Nx = 240$, three values of $ny_1 = (20, 25, 30)$
451 have been simulated. These corresponds to a total number of nodes in the y -direction
452 of $Ny = (60, 70, 80)$. In next figures, the inverse of the total number of nodes on
453 the coordinate direction on which the sensitivity is being analysed, will be used for
454 the x -axis to see the convergence of the solution. The corresponding mixing efficiency
455 together with the error bars given by the GCI procedure is provided in Fig. 9(a). The
456 grid with $ny_1 = 25$ nodes gives an acceptable discretisation error of 3.5%, thus is chosen
457 as the optimal one. Once ny_1 is fixed to 25, different values of ny_2 are tested. The
458 number of nodes in the x direction is fixed to $Nx = 240$ again. The ny_2 has been
459 ranged as $ny_2 = (15, 20, 15)$, which corresponds to $Ny = (65, 70, 75)$. The mesh with
460 $ny_2 = 20$ yields a discretisation error of 3.9%, so this is chosen as the optimal one
461 (see Fig. 9(b)). Finally, the value for Nx is ranged between $Nx = (220, 240, 260, 280)$,
462 whilst ny_1 and ny_2 are fixed to the said optimal values. As can be seen in Fig. 9(c),
463 the effect of the different grids on the efficiency is quite low, and an intermediate value
464 of $Nx = 240$ is finally chosen. Therefore, for $h = 0.4$ the optimal grid selected is
465 $(ny_1, ny_2, Nx) = (25, 20, 240)$, which means a total of $Ny \times Nx = 70 \times 240$ nodes.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 9: Grid convergence study to select the number of nodes for: (a) ny_1 ; (b) ny_2 ; and (c) Nx . $h = 0.4$, $Re = 200$, $Pe = 200$. The blue dots are the CFD values obtained for each mesh, whereas the error bars are the discretisation error (Grid Convergence Index) due to the refinement. The red dashed line is the expected value of $\langle \eta \rangle$ towards the Richardson extrapolated value (red square marker).

466 Regarding the inlet of medium size, $h = 0.2$, the GCI study was initialised with fixed
 467 values of $ny_1 = 15$ and $Nx = 240$, and three values of $ny_2 = (30, 40, 50)$, corresponding
 468 to $Ny = (60, 70, 80)$. The corresponding mixing efficiency together with the error bars
 469 given by the GCI procedure are shown in Fig. 10(a). The grid with $ny_2 = 40$ nodes gives
 470 an acceptable discretisation error of 1.4%, and is chosen as the optimal option. Next,
 471 three different values of ny_1 are simulated with fixed $Nx = 240$: $ny_1 = (16, 21, 26)$,
 472 which corresponds to $Ny = (72, 82, 92)$. The mesh with $ny_2 = 21$ yields a discretisation
 473 error of 3.3%, so this is accepted as optimal option, see Fig. 10(b). Finally, the value

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 10: Grid convergence study to select the number of nodes for: (a) ny_1 ; (b) ny_2 ; and (c) Nx . $h = 0.2$, $Re = 200$, $Pe = 200$. The blue dots are the CFD values obtained for each mesh, whereas the error bars are the discretisation error (Grid Convergence Index) due to the refinement. The red dashed line is the expected value of $\langle \eta \rangle$ towards the Richardson extrapolated value (red square marker).

474 for Nx is selected from $Nx = (200, 240, 280)$, whereas ny_1 and ny_2 are the fixed optimal
 475 values. The medium mesh with an acceptable error of around 1.5% is selected as the
 476 optimal one (see Fig. 10(c)), which corresponds to $Nx = 240$. Therefore, for $h = 0.2$ the
 477 optimal grid is $(ny_1, ny_2, Nx) = (21, 40, 240)$, which means a total of $Ny \times Nx = 82 \times 240$
 478 nodes.

479 Finally, for $h = 0.1$, the GCI was conducted for ny_1 with $Nx = 200$ and $ny_2 =$
 480 80. The values of ny_1 simulated were ranged as $ny_1 = (10, 15, 20)$, corresponding
 481 to $Ny = (100, 110, 120)$. As can be observed in Fig. 11(a), the medium value of

482 $ny_1 = 15$ nodes gives a very acceptable discretisation error of 0.05%. Next, three values
 483 of ny_2 were tested: $ny_2 = (40, 60, 80)$, with $ny_1 = 15$ and $Nx = 200$ as fixed values.
 484 This scenario corresponds to $Ny = (70, 90, 110)$. In this case, given that the solid
 485 wall between both inlets is the highest ($0.8H$), the finest grid with $ny_2 = 80$ with a
 486 discretisation error of 0.1% was selected (see Fig. 11(b)). To conclude the GCI analysis,
 487 the value of nx was ranged as $Nx = (180, 220, 260)$. The medium mesh with $Nx = 220$
 488 nodes with a discretisation error of 2.3% was finally selected as the optimal option,
 489 whose performance can be seen in Fig. 11(c). Therefore, for $h = 0.1$, the optimal
 490 grid has $(ny_1, ny_2, Nx) = (15, 80, 220)$ as nodal distribution, which means a total of
 491 $Ny \times Nx = 110 \times 220$ nodes.

492 Regarding the time integration, the stability of the explicit scheme to advance in
 493 time the transport Equations (6) and (7) was assured by choosing a time step for the
 494 Courant-Friedrich-Lewis number to be much lower than unity. This has been done so
 495 for the most unfavourable configuration ($Re = 200$ and $Pe = 200$) on each geometric
 496 configuration. This dimensionless number for every cell i, j , based on the magnitude
 497 velocity $|\vec{v}_{i,j}|$ and the grid cell diagonal, is evaluated as

$$CFL = \frac{\Delta t \sqrt{|\vec{v}_{i,j}|}}{\sqrt{\Delta x_{i,j}^2 + \Delta y_{i,j}^2}}. \quad (23)$$

498 Once the time step is chosen in order to keep $CFL < 1 \forall i, j$, it is fixed for the other
 499 Reynolds and Peclet-like numbers. In particular, for $h = 0.1$ the highest Courant was
 500 around 0.3; for $h = 0.2$, the maximum was around 0.1; and for $h = 0.4$, it was around
 501 0.025. In all configurations, these maximum values appear close to the inlets, where
 502 the velocities are the highest and the grid cells the smallest.

503 3. Results

504 The performance of the parallel wall jets for laminar mixing purposes can be assessed
 505 from different viewpoints. Although the mixing efficiency can be improved by, for
 506 instance, the aggregation of obstacles or the increase in the length of the channel, this

Figure 11: Grid convergence study to select the number of nodes for: (a) ny_1 ; (b) ny_2 ; and (c) Nx . $h = 0.1$, $Re = 200$, $Pe = 200$. The blue dots are the CFD values obtained for each mesh, whereas the error bars are the discretisation error (Grid Convergence Index) due to the refinement. The red dashed line is the expected value of $\langle \eta \rangle$ towards the Richardson extrapolated value (red square marker).

507 would lead to an increase in pressure drop too. The higher the pressure drop, the less
 508 efficient the mixing machine would be, since a high pumping power requirement may
 509 be not practical for certain applications. It is hence expected a high mixing efficiency
 510 at a low pumping power need. For the objective to analyse in detail the performance of
 511 the mixing machines at different working conditions and geometrical configurations, in
 512 this section will be analysed the effect on mixing efficiency, pressure drop (and mixing
 513 energy cost) and the effect of the length of the channel.

514 *3.1. Effect on Mixing Efficiency*

515 In terms of mixing performance, it has been observed how the Reynolds number Re ,
516 Peclet-like number Pe , and dimensionless blockage ratio (wall jet width) h affect the
517 mixing efficiency. As expected, the lower the h , the more efficient the mixing is, since
518 the jets have more time to grow separately before they are in contact. This leads to
519 a very decent mixing even without vortex shedding, and specially remarkable for low
520 Pe , due to the molecular/thermal diffusion effects. Diffusion is dominant in flows with
521 low viscosity (low Peclet-like, i.e. high Schmidt number for molecular diffusion or high
522 Prandtl number for thermal diffusion). This performance is shown in Fig. 12.

523 It can be observed in Fig. 12 that when Pe is increased, the mixing efficiency is
524 greater for smaller values of h . This effect is not strictly due to the Pe itself, but the
525 geometry. That is, the behaviour of the flow across the channel is highly affected by the
526 dimensionless blockage, leading to configurations with and without downstream oscillations.
527 This performance is summarised in Fig. 13, where the micromixer configurations
528 that lead to oscillatory structures are represented by circles. At the background, contours
529 of the peak-to-peak value of η (η_{pp}) are plotted. These contours represent the
530 amplitude of the oscillation of η . As aforesaid in fluids with high Pe , $h = 0.4$ geometries
531 yielded lower mixing efficiency than $h = 0.1$ and $h = 0.2$. The reason is that for those
532 geometries with $h < 0.4$, the oscillatory downstream flow enhances mixing, opposite to
533 $h = 0.4$, which has barely oscillation (see Fig. 13 and the colorbar scale). It can be
534 actually seen that in Fig. 12(a), $Re = 60$ is less efficient than higher Reynolds because
535 that configuration did not present an oscillatory flow in Fig. 13(a). Likewise, one can
536 extract the same conclusions between Figs. 12(b) and 13(b).

537 Whilst one expects a high η_{pp} for configurations leading to high η , the situation is
538 actually the opposite upon comparison between Figs. 12 and 13. This is because diffu-
539 sivity (mixing by diffusion) is more dominant than mechanical mixing (vortex mixing)
540 in this type of problem. This is evidenced in the high Pe case, which has less dominance
541 of diffusion. In this scenario, the higher values of Pe lead to high values of η_{pp} , which
542 correspond to high values of η .

(a) $h = 0.1$

(b) $h = 0.2$

(c) $h = 0.4$

Figure 12: Efficiency as function of Re and Pe for different configurations of the jets: (a) $h = 0.1$; (b) $h = 0.2$; and (c) $h = 0.4$.

543 The more intense the oscillatory motion of the vortex streets, the better the mixing.
 544 The oscillations appearing for each configuration can be observed in Figs. 14-16. As
 545 discussed before for the Reynolds numbers considered in this work, configurations with
 546 low h values tend to exhibit more intense oscillations. Configurations with $h = 0.4$
 547 exhibit no oscillation, and mixing is entirely attributed to thermal/molecular diffusion.
 548 This makes important to know beforehand whether a configuration may or may not lead
 549 to downstream oscillations. There are previous works in the literature on the prediction
 550 of this of behavior by means of Machine Learning models in flows around objects to

Figure 13: Appearance of Vortex Streets (VS) and peak-to-peak mixing efficiency value as function of Re and Pe for different configurations of the jets: (a) $h = 0.1$; (b) $h = 0.2$; and (c) $h = 0.4$. For $h = 0.1$ and $h = 0.2$ the highest values of η_{pp} are located in test cases with vortex shedding at high Re and Pe . The values of η_{pp} in $h = 0.4$ are too low to extract conclusions, as there is no vortex shedding in any test case configuration.

551 lead to vortex shedding-based mixing [20].

552 The impact of the oscillatory motion seen in Figs. 14-16 on the mixing can be
 553 inferred by comparison with Figs. 17-22, where results with the smallest and highest
 554 Pe , together with the smallest, mid and highest Re are shown. For $Re = 60$, it was
 555 shown in Fig. 13 that none of the geometries lead to downstream oscillations, thus this
 556 mixing is very dependent on Pe and almost entirely independent on h . When the Re is

(a) $Re = 60$

(b) $Re = 120$

(c) $Re = 200$

Figure 14: Instantaneous streamlines at different Reynolds numbers for the geometry $h = 0.1$. The upper flow is coloured as a blue wall jet, and the lower wall jet is coloured in red. The streamline patterns are different because the higher the Reynolds number, the more intense the oscillatory motion. For $Re = 60$ the flow downstream is steady.

557 set to an intermediate value of $Re = 120$, $h = 0.1$ and $h = 0.2$ exhibit oscillations, but
 558 $h = 0.4$ does not. Nevertheless, if $Pe = 50$, all configurations yield a perfect mixing.
 559 However, for the unfavourable case scenario of $Pe = 200$, only the $h = 0.1$ geometry
 560 achieves (very quickly in spatial terms) a full mixing, thanks to the intense wavy flow,
 561 see Fig. 14(b). The $h = 0.2$ geometry achieves a better mixing than $h = 0.4$, but
 562 still very inefficient due to the low intensity oscillations, see Fig. 15(b). For $Re = 200$
 563 the performance of the mixing machine is nearly the same as in $Re = 120$ in terms of
 564 mixing efficiency. In principle, it does not seem necessary to increase that much the
 565 Reynolds number to improve mixing. This increase in Reynolds number will have an
 566 important increase in the required pumping power, as will be shown next.

Figure 15: Instantaneous streamlines at different Reynolds numbers for the geometry $h = 0.2$. The upper wall jet is coloured in blue, and the lower wall jet is coloured in red. The streamline patterns are different because the higher the Reynolds number, the more intense the oscillatory motion. For $Re = 60$ the flow downstream is steady. For $Re = 120$ the flow downstream is nearly steady.

567 3.2. Effect on Pressure Drop and Mixing Energy Cost

568 The effect on pressure drop (and hence on the required pumping power) is depicted
 569 in Fig. 23. Due to it is a pure mechanical parameter, it does not depend on Pe .
 570 It can be seen that the pressure requirement varies depending on the configuration.
 571 For the most efficient mixing geometry, $h = 0.1$, the trend of the pressure drop when
 572 increasing the Reynolds number is parabolic-like. The minimum pressure is achieved
 573 for a Reynolds number between $Re = 120$ and $Re = 140$. Must be taken into account
 574 that the mixing was almost the same for $Re = 120$ and $Re = 200$, so the mixing energy
 575 cost will be a good reference for the selection of the ideal geometry and conditions, as
 576 will be shown next. For $h = 0.1$ and $h = 0.2$ geometries, the behaviour of the pressure
 577 drop is almost nearly decreasing when increasing the Reynolds number. This monotone

Figure 16: Instantaneous streamlines at different Reynolds numbers for the geometry $h = 0.4$. The upper wall jet is coloured in blue, and the lower wall jet is coloured in red. All streamlines reflect steady flows.

578 decreasing trend is actually parabolic too, but the range of Reynolds numbers analysed
 579 for these geometries is not large enough to show the increase expected for higher Re
 580 values.

581 Finally, the mixing energy cost is shown in Fig. 24. It is observed that the trend is
 582 actually the same as seen for the pumping power. This is because the results observed
 583 for the mixing efficiency were not dramatically affected by the Reynolds number at each
 584 geometry as long as there is no change in the oscillatory performance of the geometry
 585 when varying Re . That is, for instance for $Re = 60$ in $h = 0.1$ there is a difference
 586 with respect to the higher Re tested (see Fig. 12), because at low Re the microdevice
 587 has no von Karman streets. From the analysis of Fig. 24 can be concluded that the
 588 best option for $h = 0.1$ geometry is a Reynolds number between $Re = 120$ and 140.

Figure 17: Instantaneous dimensionless mixing quantity contours for $Re = 60$ and $Pe = 50$. The upper wall jet is at $Y = 1$ (dark red), and the lower wall jet is at $Y = 0$ (dark blue). All mixing machines achieved the maximum mixing efficiency before the channel exit ($x = 12$), as $Y = 0.5$. The mixer of geometry $h = 0.1$ achieved a perfect mixing earlier than the other configurations.

589 In Fig. 12(a) was depicted the mixing efficiency, which was $\sim 100\%$ for this geometry.
 590 For $h = 0.2$ and $h = 0.4$, $Re = 200$ seems the most efficient option amongst the tested
 591 Reynolds numbers. The configuration with the smaller mixing energy cost is $h = 0.2$
 592 with $Re = 200$. But this configuration yields lower mixing efficiency η than any $h = 0.1$
 593 for the tested $Re > 60$. Obviously, for any configuration, the lower the Pe , the lower
 594 the mixing energy cost.

595 3.3. Effect on the Strouhal Number

596 Depending on the geometry and Reynolds number, the frequency of the oscillation
 597 may vary. As aforementioned, vortex shedding is actually nonexistent for the $h = 0.4$
 598 geometry in the range of $Re \in [60, 200]$. For this reason, in Fig. 25 only the Strouhal

(a) $h = 0.1$

(b) $h = 0.2$

(c) $h = 0.4$

Figure 18: Instantaneous dimensionless mixing quantity contours for $Re = 60$ and $Pe = 200$. The upper wall jet is at $Y = 1$ (dark red), and the lower wall jet is at $Y = 0$ (dark blue). None of the mixing machines achieved the perfect mixing efficiency before the channel exit ($x = 12$), as the profile of Y is not of constant value 0.5 from a certain position x on.

599 number of the mixing efficiency η for $h = 0.1$ and $h = 0.2$ do appear. It is clear
600 that, from a critical Reynolds number on, the frequency of the oscillation decreases
601 monotonically as the Reynolds number increases, for both $h = 0.1$ and $h = 0.2$. As
602 discussed in [1], the values of the Strouhal number cannot be related to a good or bad
603 mixing in principle. They just provide a dimensionless reference on the frequency of
604 the oscillation, and the amplitude may be either large or small.

605 3.4. Effect of Channel Length

606 The length of the channel affects dramatically the mixed outflow. The longer the
607 microchannel, the higher the mixing. This is obvious, since in a long microchannel the
608 flow has more time to mix by the effect of vorticity and diffusion. To take the length of

Figure 19: Instantaneous dimensionless mixing quantity contours for $Re = 120$ and $Pe = 50$. The upper wall jet is at $Y = 1$ (dark red), and the lower wall jet is at $Y = 0$ (dark blue). All mixing machines achieved the maximum mixing efficiency before the channel exit ($x = 12$), as $Y = 0.5$. The performance of the mixer of geometry $h = 0.1$ stands out, as the perfect mixing is achieved at $x \approx 3$.

609 the channel into account, the expression given in Equation (14) allows to evaluate the
 610 difference in mixing efficiency between two positions. In particular, the difference will
 611 be evaluated between the channel outlet and a relevant position of $x = 5$ as:

$$\Delta\eta = \eta_{outlet} - \eta_{x=5}, \quad (24)$$

612 where η_{outlet} is the mixing efficiency evaluated at the outlet (the η discussed throughout
 613 the paper) and $\eta_{x=5}$ is the mixing efficiency at $x = 5$. This quantity $\Delta\eta$ is useful
 614 to predict the contribution in mixing of a portion of channel (in this analysis, the
 615 microchannel has a total length of 12 units, so we are evaluating the impact of an
 616 extra length of 7 units). The results from this evaluation are depicted in Fig. 26. It is
 617 very obvious that the $h = 0.1$ geometry exhibits the lowest impact on mixing efficiency

Figure 20: Instantaneous dimensionless mixing quantity contours for $Re = 120$ and $Pe = 200$. The upper wall jet is at $Y = 1$ (dark red), and the lower wall jet is at $Y = 0$ (dark blue). Only the $h = 0.1$ mixing machine achieved the maximum mixing efficiency before the channel exit (at $x \approx 5.8$). The $h = 0.2$ mixing device achieved an oscillatory state, resulting in a better performance than the $h = 0.4$ one.

618 when increasing the channel length. Thus a very short channel could have been used,
 619 specially for a low Peclet-like number. To understand the contribution to the total
 620 mixing efficiency, one can see Fig. 27. In this figure it is shown the mixing achieved at
 621 $x = 5$ (blue) and the mixing due to the additional channel length (orange). The sum
 622 of these two quantities yields the total mixing η at the outlet. From this figure can
 623 be seen that for $h = 0.2$ and $h = 0.4$, $\Delta\eta$ is nearly constant. However, the $h = 0.1$
 624 geometry provides nearly the 100% of the mixing efficiency at $x = 5$ for $Re = 200$,
 625 which is a case scenario of intense downstream oscillations. Thus, for this geometry a
 626 very short channel would be enough to get a highly efficient mixing performance. This
 627 would also reduce the pressure drop notably.

Figure 21: Instantaneous dimensionless mixing quantity contours for $Re = 200$ and $Pe = 50$. The upper wall jet is at $Y = 1$ (dark red), and the lower wall jet is at $Y = 0$ (dark blue). All mixing machines achieved the maximum mixing efficiency before the channel exit ($x = 12$), as $Y = 0.5$. The mixer of geometry $h = 0.1$ achieved a perfect mixing much earlier than the other configurations.

628 4. Conclusions

629 This paper has presented the novel use of two parallel wall jets as passive elements to
 630 enhance mixing mechanically by promoting flow oscillations in heat/mass exchangers.
 631 The parallel wall jets are constrained in a microchannel, which can be a device with
 632 potential use as scalable mixing device. Different channel ratios (wall jet widths) h have
 633 been tested numerically with a verified&validated CFD code based on non-uniform finite
 634 difference approximation.

635 From the analysis carried out in the paper, can be concluded that a small channel
 636 ratio of $h = 0.1$ is more beneficial to enhance mixing. The reason is that intense flow
 637 oscillations take place, which enhances mixing notably. Full mixing in this configuration

Figure 22: Instantaneous dimensionless mixing quantity contours for $Re = 200$ and $Pe = 200$. The upper wall jet is at $Y = 1$ (dark red), and the lower wall jet is at $Y = 0$ (dark blue). Only the $h = 0.1$ mixing machine achieved the maximum mixing efficiency before the channel exit (at $x \approx 9$). The $h = 0.2$ mixing device achieved an oscillatory state, resulting in a better performance than the $h = 0.4$ one.

638 is happening quite early, which allows to shorten the channel length considerably and
 639 require a lower pumping power consumption. The tested $h = 0.2$ and $h = 0.4$ geometries
 640 yielded unsatisfactory mixing efficiency results in contrast to $h = 0.1$. The reason
 641 behind is the well-known fact that both the Reynolds number and geometry play an
 642 important role in boosting or damping the flow oscillations. Actually, to achieve a
 643 non-steady simulation for $h = 0.4$ one has to increase the Reynolds number above
 644 $Re = 400$. For the most promising configuration, $h = 0.1$, it has been observed also
 645 that the pumping power achieved its minimum between $Re = 120$ and 140 . Since the
 646 mixing efficiency was nearly the same for these Reynolds numbers and $Re = 200$, an
 647 optimal performance would be within that range. Upon a channel length analysis, it

Figure 23: Pressure drop for each configuration as function of Re for different configurations of the jets.

648 has been also noticed that for fluids with a Peclet-like number between 50 and 200, and
 649 regimes between Reynolds 120 and 140, the channel length can be shortened at least
 650 to a length of 5 units and keep nearly the same outlet mixing efficiency. This reduces
 651 the pressure drop, and thence, the mixing efficiency cost.

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(a) $h = 0.1$

(b) $h = 0.2$

(c) $h = 0.4$

Figure 24: Mixing energy cost as function of Re and Pe for different configurations of the jets: (a) $h = 0.1$; (b) $h = 0.2$; and (c) $h = 0.4$.

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Figure 26: Instantaneous efficiency difference $\Delta\eta$ as function of Re and Pe for different configurations of the jets: (a) $h = 0.1$; and (b) $h = 0.2$; and (c) $h = 0.4$.

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Figure 27: Instantaneous outlet mixing efficiency ($\eta_{x=5} + \Delta\eta$) and efficiency difference $\Delta\eta$ for different extreme combinations of Re and Pe . Both the mixing efficiency and efficiency difference are provided in % units.

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866 **Appendix A. Streamfunction-vorticity boundary conditions.**

867 The corresponding boundary conditions to solve Equations (5)–(6) are:

868 **Inlet ($x = 0$).** At the inlet, the flow fully developed (parabolic). This means that the
869 components of the velocity are known:

870 Primitive variables: $\vec{v}^{in} = (u^{in}, 0, 0)$;

$$u^{in} = \begin{cases} \frac{6}{(1+\alpha)h^3}y(h-y), & 0 \leq y \leq h, \\ \frac{6\alpha}{(1+\alpha)(\beta h)^3}(y-h')(1-y), & h' \leq y \leq 1. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

871 Non-primitive variables:

$$\psi^{in} = \int_0^y u^{in} dy, \quad \omega^{in} = -u_y^{in} + v_x = -u_y^{in} + \psi_{xx_0}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

872 The subscript xx_0 (or else yy_0) means a finite difference approximation of the
873 second derivative with null first derivative because of $\psi_x = 0 = v$ (or $\psi_y = 0 = u$).

874 **Solid wall ($y = \text{constant}$).** At horizontal walls, the components of the velocity are
875 known:

876 Primitive variables: $\vec{v}^{wall} = (0, 0, 0)$;

877 Non-primitive variables:

$$\psi^{wall} = \text{constant}, \quad \omega^{wall} = -u_y + v_x = -u_y = -\psi_{yy_0} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

878 since on the wall $v = v_x = 0$ and $u = \psi_y = 0$.

879 **Solid wall ($x = \text{constant}$).** At vertical walls, the components of the velocity are known:

880 Primitive variables: $\vec{v}^{wall} = (0, 0, 0)$;

881 Non-primitive variables:

$$\psi^{wall} = \text{constant}, \quad \omega^{wall} = -u_y + v_x = v_x = \psi_{xx_0}, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

882 since on the wall $u = u_y = 0$ and $v = \psi_x = 0$.

883 **Outlet ($x = \text{constant}$).** At the outlet, outflow conditions in terms of null derivatives
 884 are imposed, which allows to obtain the value at the boundary in terms of up-
 885 stream known values:

886 Primitive variables: $v_x = 0$;

887 Non-primitive variables:

$$\psi_{xx} = 0 = \omega_{xx}. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

888 **Appendix B. Mass fraction/Temperature boundary conditions.**

889 To solve Equation (7) one has to take into account the boundary conditions that,
 890 on the different boundaries, are given by:

Inlet ($x = 0$).

$$0 \leq y \leq h : Y^{in} = 0; \quad (\text{B.1})$$

891

$$H - h \leq y \leq H : Y^{in} = 1; \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Solid wall ($y = \text{constant}$):

$$Y_x^{wall} = 0; \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Solid wall ($x = \text{constant}$):

$$Y_y^{wall} = 0; \quad (\text{B.4})$$

892 **Outlet ($x = \text{constant}$):** Null Newmann condition at the outlet:

$$Y_x = 0. \quad (\text{B.5})$$

893 **Appendix C. Pressure boundary conditions**

894 The boundary conditions to solve Equation (9) can be derived from the momentum
 895 equation. They can be written as [69]:

$$\vec{v}_t + (\vec{v} \cdot \nabla) \vec{v} = -\nabla p - \frac{1}{Re} \nabla \wedge \vec{\Omega}, \quad (\text{C.1})$$

896 from which the corresponding normal gradient to a boundary can be known. Therefore,
897 on the different boundaries one can obtain:

Inlet/Outlet ($x = \text{constant}$).

$$p_x = -\frac{1}{Re}\omega_y - (uu_x + vu_y) - u_t; \quad (\text{C.2})$$

Solid wall ($y = \text{constant}$).

$$p_y = \frac{1}{Re}\omega_x; \quad (\text{C.3})$$

Solid wall ($x = \text{constant}$).

$$p_x = -\frac{1}{Re}\omega_y; \quad (\text{C.4})$$

898 Finally, to be able to solve Equation (9) and in order to obtain a unique pressure
899 distribution, a reference pressure value must be given at an arbitrary point [70]. In
900 particular, an arbitrary value of 5 units has been set at the middle of the domain.